

ELEVATING OFFSHORE RENEWABLE ENERGY: A STUDY ON INTEGRATING WIND, SOLAR, AND STORAGE SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The aggregation of various renewable energy sources within an offshore energy park can maximize the use of marine space and of existing electrical infrastructure but poses the challenge of combined intermittencies and curtailment. In many places, conditions allow for offshore floating solar panels to be deployed in and around wind parks. Since 2022 these technologies have already been demonstrated in a number of offshore pilots in the North Sea and Yellow Sea. This paper investigates how solar can complement wind for a Mediterranean energy park with offshore transmission cable capacity as a constraint. The added value of energy storage is then investigated by considering various storage control strategies for different capacities of energy storage. It is shown that the addition of a solar capacity that equals that of installed wind power can increase the annual exported production by more than 30% without export capacity constraint and by nearly 23% when the export capacity equals the installed wind capacity.

1 Introduction

The integration of offshore floating solar panels and energy storage systems with offshore wind parks is an innovative approach to enhance renewable energy generation, improve energy security, and optimize the use of marine space. Feasibility studies as well as research and demonstration projects that explore the potential of these offshore multi-source parks have emerged recently. The EU-SCORES project[1], a Horizon 2020 Green Deal project, started in 2021 and aims to enable multi-source offshore energy parks across Europe by 2025. For this purpose, the project aims to improve the maturity of both wave and offshore solar technologies, while demonstrating integration potential with offshore wind. To date, the project has published a number of studies on LCOE analyses, Renewable Correlation of offshore resources, Grid value of co-located offshore renewable energy, Dimensioning and optimization of multi-source offshore renewable energy parks. A design study published by van der Zant et al. demonstrates a multi-source park in the Dutch North Sea, combining wind, wave and solar production. The study shows that the co-location of wind, solar and wave energy sources increases the extracted energy density by 22%, making more efficient use of the limited available marine space[2]. Moreover, it found that the park output becomes smoother as the yearly-averaged coefficient of variation decreases by 13%, the export cable capacity factor with respect to the export cable increases by 19%, and the hours where the output of the park is below 20% of the export cable capacity decreases by 86.5%.

The Dutch SENSE-HUB project[3] focuses on integrating offshore wind, solar, and hydrogen production at sea to enhance the Dutch North Sea's energy system. The project will involve several activities including demonstrating an improved offshore solar system in the North Sea, studying the environmental impacts of hybrid energy parks through monitoring and modelling as well as validating its concept by developing of the techno-economic system designs at GW-scale. The aim is to demonstrate that the integration of different renewable energy sources can produce a more constant supply and have higher amounts of green hydrogen production at lower costs.

A study by M. López, N. Rodríguez, and G. Iglesias [4] explores the integration of offshore wind and solar PV in Asturias, Spain, demonstrating significant potential in combining these two renewable sources. The study shows an increase in installed capacity in the same area by a factor 10 and energy output by a factor of 7. This integration also smoothed the power output variability, achieving a 63% improvement in the Power Smoothing Index.

In the Netherlands, Feasibility Studies on Hybrid Offshore Solar and Wind Systems[5] have been conducted focusing on integrating floating solar with an existing 752 MW offshore wind installation. The integration was found to be technically and economically beneficial, allowing for shared grid connection with minimal curtailment.

The study revealed that adding solar power could utilize the same offshore to onshore grid connection effectively, with only about 1.72% of solar energy potentially needing curtailment due to cable capacity limitations. This indicates a high synergy between wind and solar power sources, optimizing the use of infrastructure and enhancing grid stability.

These examples illustrate the broad interest and ongoing research in combining offshore floating solar panels and energy storage with offshore wind parks.

After around 25 years of bottom fixed offshore wind projects, starting in the North Sea, the increasing maturity of floating wind technologies is also driving plans for offshore wind projects in other regions with deeper waters. In 2023 the French government published information on 2 sites for a total of 1.5 GW of offshore wind capacity in the Mediterranean Sea. [6] Subsequently, the tendering of the substations of these wind power plants was started later in the same year. [7]

The present study explores the potential for one of these sites to optimise energy production through a hybrid system, combining offshore wind and offshore solar energy. Furthermore, the addition of storage capacity to further improve the power profile of the park is studied in a time series model.

2. Methodology

To calculate the potential output of the wind park with the solar power and storage added we used DMEC's in-house Python-based simulation model - multiORE. The multiORE model combines renewable energy production models to describe offshore renewable energy parks. Based on local resources, obtained from hindcast data as well as satellite measurements, different park configurations can be defined, and the power output of each energy source can be computed. The model results depend on the geographical characteristics of each offshore renewable energy park. The modelled features include low production hours, curtailment, export cable capacity factor and power smoothing, the aspect definitions are clarified in the further text.

Physical Model

Fig. 1 multiORE model structure

The multiORE model calculates hourly the electricity production of different offshore renewable energy sources at a given location. Based on the type of generating assets (e.g. wind turbine model, offshore solar concept), the multi-source park is analysed.

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Wind calculations

The total installed wind power capacity considered was 250 MW in the first phase of the project and 750MW in the second. To compute the total wind energy output, we have used a NREL 15MW offshore wind turbine power curve[8] (Figure 2) with the cut-in, cut-out and rated wind speed respectively at 4m/s, 25m/s and 11 m/s and multiplied their output depending on the wind speed by the number of turbines in the wind park. In the first part of this study, the park has 17 of these turbines and 50 in the second, the total wind power output profile is made of the summation of each wind turbine contribution, with an overall wake effect assumed at 10%.

Fig. 2 NREL 15MW wind turbine power curve

Solar calculation

The power generation from PV panels is determined by the following formula:

$$P_{PV} = eff \cdot A \cdot H \cdot PR$$

Where P_{PV} is the power generated by the PV system, eff is the PV efficiency that is air temperature and irradiation dependent, A is area covered by PV panels in m^2 , H is the incoming irradiation in W/m^2 that is tilt and orientation angle of the PV installation dependent and PR is a performance ratio that takes into account factors like availability (due to

maintenance and repairs), annual degradation, soiling, and losses due to DC to AC conversion.

We considered a base efficiency of 22% for the solar panels which is then recalculated depending on the panel's temperature. The panel's temperature calculation accounts for heat loss/gain depending on wind speed, air temperature and incoming irradiation. The panel's efficiency is then adjusted based on whether its temperature exceeds a standard operating condition. If the temperature is higher, the efficiency decreases; otherwise, it remains constant.

To calculate the area covered by PV panels and since we considered a base efficiency of 22% there is approximately 220 W per square meter of installed PV power resulting in an area of 1.136 km² covered by PV panels in the first phase of the project and 3.409 km² in the second. Knowing that the entire area of the project site for the first and the second phases of the project is respectively 48 km² and 48+96 km² means that the PV panels account for 2.4% of the site area in both cases.

In the first scenario, we have calculated solar power production of PV installation placed horizontally. To increase the production of PV panels they should be placed at the tilt and orientation angle that increases solar radiation capture. For the chosen location in the observed period, to elevate solar radiation capture we have considered panels placed at the angle of 30 degrees oriented to the south.

To compute PR, we considered an availability factor of 0.95, a soiling factor of 0.9, 0.98 and 0.97 for the factors accounting for the DC and AC losses and an average annual degradation factor of 0.94 (a system with a lifetime of 25 years with a 0.5% degradation per year was considered). That brings the total PR to 0.76.

Storage calculation

We have utilized different storage control algorithms, charging and discharging based on various rules which will further be specified. We modelled the storage system with a trip-around efficiency of 81%, assuming 10% losses both at the charging and discharging process. The storage c-rate of 1, matched the battery power to its capacity so it can both charge and discharge fully within 1 hour.

Project site

We have chosen one of the locations tendered by the French government, located 25 from the coast of Narbonne.

Fig. 3 Sites for Mediterranean floating wind projects [6]

We have used satellite weather data including wind speed and solar irradiation data as well as the air temperature for the period from January 15th, 2020, to December 31st, 2023.[9]

The key characteristics of the raw resource data for the mentioned period at the location of the selected French project are:

Average wind speed at hub height [m/s]: 7.96 m/s

Yearly global horizontal radiation [kWh/m²/year]: 1515

We have recalculated the wind speed at hub height (150 m for the earlier mentioned NREL 15MW offshore wind turbine) using a logarithmic wind profile [10] and based on that wind speed created a Weibull probability distribution of wind speed at the hub height shown in Figure 4.

We present the distribution of global horizontal irradiation (GHI) values greater than zero in the histogram of Figure 5. The horizontal axis distributes the GHI values into 30 bins, while the vertical axis represents the relative frequency of these values. Each "event" or measurement in the dataset corresponds to a one-hour time block, however, the hours when the GHI value is 0 (the night hours) have been excluded.

Fig. 4 Weibull probability distribution of wind speed at the hub height

Export Infrastructure

We have taken the value of 750 MW for export infrastructure that is planned by the projects. It has been considered that in some park designs, ‘overplanting’ could be utilised, where the installed generation capacity exceeds that of the export infrastructure. Due to the natural offset of wind and sun, it is expected that only in a few cases both PV systems and wind turbines will operate at full capacity. This leads to so-called ‘curtailment’, which corresponds to turning off generating assets to protect the electrical infrastructure from overloading. This can be an economic consideration, which saves investments in larger cables or transformers while losing a small portion of the potential electricity or it can present an opportunity to integrate energy storage and save the energy that would otherwise be curtailed. Such strategic integration would not only reduce waste through curtailment but also ensure a more constant and reliable energy supply.

Proposed Scenarios To analyse and quantify wind park production results as well as the changes that come with the integration of solar power and energy storage, we created several scenarios that would be analysed and compared in the remainder of this study .

Scenario 1 -Wind+Solar without curtailment:

- 250 MW wind - This scenario represents the first phase of project development where the wind power capacity is at 250 MW while the export infrastructure capacity is already at its full capacity of 750 MW, focusing on harnessing wind energy without any solar power complement.
- 250 MW wind + 250 MW solar (horizontal) - Integrates solar energy with wind, adding a 250MW solar power plant with panels placed horizontally, aiming for simplicity in installation but potentially sacrificing efficiency in energy capture.

Fig. 5 Distribution of global horizontal irradiation (GHI) for GHI>0

- 250 MW wind + 250 MW solar (optimal angle for south orientation) - Combines wind with solar energy where solar panels are oriented at an optimal angle towards the south to maximize solar radiation capture, enhancing solar energy production.

Scenario 2 - Wind+Solar with curtailment:

- 750 MW wind -Baseline scenario featuring full scale 750 MW wind power plant.
- 750 MW wind + 750MW solar (optimal angle for south orientation) - Expands the power plant to its full capacity with equal contributions from wind and optimally placed solar panels, testing the limits of the export infrastructure's capacity.

Scenario 3- Storage:

- Scenario 3 explores the benefits of storage integration into the system described in Scenario 2. Sensitivity studies are conducted on storage capacity for different control strategies.

Each scenario explores different configurations and technologies to optimize energy production, efficiency, and integration of a multi-source offshore power plant, reflecting on various strategies to enhance renewable energy utility and grid compatibility.

Low and High Production Hours

We have defined low production hours as the hours during which the production is under 20% of the full capacity of the export infrastructure. Reducing this number can strengthen energy security and smoothness of the export output profiles. Similarly, high production hours have been defined as the hours during which the production is over 80% of the capacity of the export infrastructure.

Export Cable Capacity Factor

The Export Cable Capacity Factor (CCF) quantifies the average electricity produced over a given period relative to its maximum potential output. In this study, we assess the CF in relation to the export cable, which reflects the amount of electricity generated in proportion to the export cable's capacity. We define the CF as follows:

$$CCF = \frac{\text{Exported energy}}{\text{Export infrastructure capacity}} \cdot 100\%$$

The CCF is expressed as a percentage [%], representing the total electrical energy generated in the park over a specific period of time [MWh] as a fraction of the maximum possible energy that the export cable can transport during the same timeframe [MWh].

Smoothness

The smoothness of the power output is determined by computing the coefficient of variation (CoV) which is calculated by dividing the standard deviation of power output by its mean value:

$$CoV = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (P_i - \mu)^2}}{\mu}$$

Fig. 6 Hourly electricity produced in one year in Scenario 1 for wind-only and wind with solar aggregation

Where P_i is the power output at the timestep i , μ is the mean of the power outputs, and N is the total number of power outputs. The lower CoV values indicate a smoother power profile.

3 Results

In **Scenario 1** the export cable capacity factor is low due to its size matching the capacity of the wind power of the second phase of the project which is three times larger than the installed wind capacity in this first phase. Adding solar PV leads to a significant increase in the exported energy (29%). Figure 6 and Figure 7 represent the hourly electricity exported and the mean monthly exported electricity for the observed period, normalized by the installed wind capacity.

With the addition of solar, there is an increase in export cable capacity factor of 4.4% compared to the export cable capacity factor in the wind-only park. This reflects the full addition of production of the solar PV modules as no curtailment occurs.

Fig. 7 Monthly Electricity Exported in Scenario 1

On a general level, the number of low production hours is high by definition, since the export infrastructure is at its full capacity while only a third of the wind capacity is installed, but the improvement with the addition of solar can be noted through the reduction in the low production hours. Results are presented in Figure 8. We can observe a shifting of long periods of low production towards significantly shorter time frames when adding solar power production. The decrease in low production hours is 29%.

Fig. 8 Distribution of Low Production Hours for One Year Period in Scenario 1

The mean annual electricity produced by the PV system placed at the tilt and orientation angle of 30° and 180° additionally increases by 5.5 %. Tilting the panel angle has decreased slightly solar production in the summer months, but increased significantly during the rest of the year, especially in winter.

In **Scenario 2**, which represents the second phase of project development where the wind power capacity is at its full capacity of 750MW while the export infrastructure capacity is unchanged (750MW), we propose adding 750MW of offshore floating solar power with the south orientation and tilt of 30 degrees to increase solar energy production as explored in in Scenario 1.

Fig10 Hourly electricity produced in the period of one year in Scenario 2

The results show a decrease in low production hours of 22.5%. The distribution of low production hours for one year period is shown in Figure 9. The number of low production hours is initially much lower than in the Scenario 1 even in the wind-only case since the export infrastructure was sized to match the wind capacity in Scenario 2.

Fig. 9 Distribution of Low Production Hours for One Year Period in Scenario 2

The hourly distribution of the production of the park for one year and the mean monthly exported electricity for the observed period normalized by the installed wind capacity is shown in Figure 10 and 11.

The Figures 10 and 11 illustrate clearly how solar generation complements wind production. The results show an increase of 31.3% in average annual electricity produced with the addition of PV power. Obviously portion of this production would have to be curtailed since it exceeds the capacity of the export infrastructure. Therefore, the average annual electricity exported would then be 22.5% increased compared to the wind-only scenario leading to an increase of the capacity factor of the export cable by 9.9% to 58%.

Fig. 11 Monthly Electricity Exported in Scenario 2

Scenario 3 explores the benefits of storage integration into the system described in the Scenario 2. Several charging and discharging control plans were considered and compared to compare how they address two challenges: the preservation of produced energy that would otherwise be curtailed as well as reduction in low production hours.

Strategy 1 - strategy that minimises curtailment

In this strategy the battery charges when curtailment occurs and discharges as soon as there is available capacity in the export infrastructure. This strategy minimizes the curtailment and maximizes the preservation of the produced electricity, however, it shows the worst results in smoothening the power profile and it doesn't significantly increase the energy exported during the low production hours.

Strategy 2 - strategy that targets low production hours

Battery is discharging during low production hours and charging as soon as baseload is ensured. The result is a maximal decrease in the low production hours, and it shows a decent improvement in the smoothness of the power output. However, the overall exported electricity and curtailment capture is decreased since a lot of energy is "trapped" in the storage and lost due to charging and discharging efficiency.

Strategy 3 - strategy that maximises smoothness

We are charging a battery during high production hours (production above 80% of the export infrastructure capacity) and discharging during low production hours. This strategy shows a significant decrease in the low production hours, but it doesn't ensure space for the electricity that would have to be curtailed. It does however show the best results in output smoothness since it has the narrowest range of desired exported output among the proposed strategies.

Strategy 4 - strategy that balances all the proposed targets

Battery charges when curtailment occurs and discharges during low production hours. The result shows a decrease in the low production hours while increasing total exported energy by preserving electricity that would otherwise be curtailed. On the other hand, this strategy doesn't optimally smoothen the output.

Described conclusions and comparison are shown in Figure 12 a), b) and c)

Figure 12 Comparison of proposed Control strategies based on (a) Percentage of Produced Energy Exported depending on the Battery Control Strategy (b) Percentage of Energy Exported during Low Production Hours depending on the Battery Control Strategy (c) Smoothness

Figure 13 illustrates the percentage of produced energy that would be directly exported, exported through the battery, lost due to battery charging and discharging efficiency and curtailed for each of these control strategies and battery capacity range from 0 to 30000 MWh increased with a step of 100MWh with each iteration.

Figure 13 The effect of different battery sizes on the percentage of energy exported directly, energy stored and later discharged from the battery, energy lost in battery conversion and energy curtailed for (a) Strategy 1 – Strategy that minimises curtailment (b) Strategy 2 – Strategy that targets low production hours (c) Strategy 3 – Strategy that maximises smoothness (d) Strategy 4 – Strategy that balances all the proposed targets

The insights from Figure 13 highlight the scalable nature of the battery storage solutions tested in various scenarios. Implementing these strategies could significantly enhance the efficiency and reliability of renewable energy systems globally, paving the way for more sustainable energy practices. But at the same time, it's shown on the plots that the losses of energy either in the form of curtailment or the battery losses can be quite significant depending on the strategy. It can also be observed that increasing the storage capacity makes sense

until a certain level, that varies for each strategy, after which the results start to stagnate, and the further improvements are minimal.

Table 1 shows how the main characteristics of a battery with the capacity of 3000 MWh vary when we implement these different battery control strategies (S1, S2, S3 and S4 stand for Strategy 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively) as well as their comparison with a scenario with no battery (NB) added.

Table 1 Main characteristics of a battery with the capacity 3000 MWh

	NB	S1	S2	S3	S4
Produced Energy Exported [%]	93.3	98.6	92	94.3	97.6
Energy Exported during Low Production Hours [%]	81.9	82.4	99.7	97.7	94.3
Smoothness (CoV) [-]	0.7	0.68	0.66	0.58	0.62
Directly Exported Electricity [%]	93.3	93.3	86.8	90.8	93.3
Electricity Exported through the battery [%]	0	3	5.4	2.8	2.1
Battery Losses [%]	0	0.7	1.3	0.6	0.5
Curtailement [%]	6.7	2.9	6.6	5.7	4

It can be observed that the produced energy exported increases by up to 5.26% with the first strategy. Energy exported during low production hours can increase to nearly 100% with the second strategy. Smoothness indicator CoV can increase by up to 17% compared to the output of the system without storage and the curtailed energy can reduce up to 2.3 times.

4 Conclusion

In this study, we have explored the integration of wind and solar power with export infrastructure and examined the potential benefits of incorporating energy storage systems. Our findings indicate that the addition of solar panels significantly enhances the export cable capacity factor of wind power plants, by up to 10% if we add the capacity of solar that matches wind capacity installed. By choosing a tilt of 30° and south orientation of the PV installation at this geographic location we can achieve an enhancement of 5.5% in solar power production. The complementary nature of wind and solar power, especially when both are operating at maximum capacity, presents a compelling case for the opportunity for energy storage solutions to manage excess production effectively. Depending on the control strategy and battery size, the exported electricity ranges from 91.9 to 98.7% of the produced energy and the energy exported during low production hours from 81.9 to 100%. The analysis of various storage strategies reveals that while there is no one-size-fits-all solution, flexibility in managing storage is crucial for maximizing energy export and smoothness and minimizing curtailement and low production hours. We used an example of a battery with a capacity of 3000MWh to show how these strategies could be combined and in one period nearly eliminate low production hours by reducing the electricity missing during the low production hours from 18.07% to only 0.26%. In the other period we could increase the exported

energy by 5.26% or smoothen the power profile by 17%. To make an informed selection of one particular strategy a lifetime impact, number of charging and discharging cycles and techno-economic analyses of the specific energy storage would be required.

This study, while extensive, is constrained by several factors that present an opportunities for further research to broader applicability of its findings. Firstly, the simulation models used rely on specific geographic and climatic data. Future research should include similar studies in different environments to assess the models' adaptability to varied solar irradiance and wind conditions. Additionally, our use of generalized technological assumptions calls for targeted studies that explore specific characteristics of different energy storage technologies. Defining specific storage types such as chemical batteries, mechanical storage or others can allow to account for factors like charging and discharging efficiency, c-rate more accurately. Also, assumptions regarding the efficiency of solar panels and wind turbines are based on current standards, which do not account for future technological advancements that could significantly alter energy production dynamics. Future work should also track technological advancements in solar panels and wind turbines to project their impact on energy production. Moreover, economic and regulatory factors, which can greatly influence the feasibility and implementation of renewable energy solutions, were not within the scope of this analysis, presenting another layer of complexity that future studies could address. Especially the control of the battery, which greatly influences life-time, battery losses and total export for different battery sizes, can show which strategy is the most economical solution for which goal.

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